

**MASKS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: CLINICAL VARIANTS AND DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES
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assistant of the department of internal medicine***Heorhitsu K.M.,****Huz S.,****Dymitrash K.****Abstract**

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic systemic autoimmune disease characterized by progressive inflammation of the synovial membrane of the joints, the development of erosive-destructive changes and extra-articular manifestations. The classic variant of the course of RA includes symmetrical damage to the small joints of the hands and feet, morning stiffness and gradual formation of deformities. However, in clinical practice, the disease often debuts atypically, masquerading as other rheumatological, infectious, neurological or degenerative pathologies. That is why the problem of "masks" of rheumatoid arthritis remains relevant in modern rheumatology.

Early diagnosis of RA is of fundamental importance, as the first months after the onset of the disease are considered a "window of therapeutic opportunity", when timely administration of basic therapy allows to slow down the progression of structural damage and improve the prognosis. However, atypical clinical variants often cause diagnostic errors and treatment delays.

Keywords: antibodies to cyclic citrullinated peptide, proinflammatory cytokines, rheumatoid factor, rheumatoid arthritis, atypical onset, seronegative arthritis, extraarticular manifestations, differential diagnosis.

Introduction

Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic systemic autoimmune disease of unknown etiology, which is based on immunoinflammatory damage to the synovial membrane of the joints with the development of chronic proliferative synovitis and gradual destruction of joint structures. Modern ideas about RA have expanded significantly: today the disease is considered not only as a joint pathology, but as a systemic immunoinflammatory process with a wide range of clinical phenotypes. The prevalence of RA in the population is about 0.5–1%, and the disease is one of the leading causes of early disability and disability [9].

The classic form of RA is characterized by symmetrical involvement of the small joints of the hands and feet, morning stiffness, and progressive erosive processes. However, atypical forms of the disease are often encountered in clinical practice, in which joint symptoms are absent or mild in the early stages. In such cases, the clinical picture may resemble other diseases, which significantly complicates diagnosis [2].

A particular difficulty in clinical practice is the so-called "masks" of RA — atypical onsets and course variants in which classical symmetrical polyarthritis is absent or mild for a long time. Such forms can mimic infectious, oncological, neurological, pulmonary, cardiac, or other rheumatic diseases, which leads to a delay in diagnosis and late initiation of basic therapy [19].

Current recommendations from the European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology and the American College of Rheumatology emphasize the need for early diagnosis of RA even in the absence of a typical clinical picture, taking into account serological, immunological, and imaging markers [22].

Clinical masks of rheumatoid arthritis include:

• **Seronegative rheumatoid arthritis** in which RF and ACCP remain negative. In such patients, the clinical picture often resembles seronegative spondyloarthritis, reactive arthritis, or osteoarthritis. The absence

of specific antibodies in the early stages complicates the verification of the diagnosis and delays the start of basic therapy. The main symptoms include: acute onset, asymmetric oligoarthritis, predominant involvement of large joints, absence or mild morning stiffness, fever, and systemic manifestations. Ultrasound of the joints, MRI of the hands, dynamic observation, and determination of anti-CCP are of diagnostic value [15].

• **Monoarthritis and oligoarthritis** can manifest as damage to one or more joints. Such a debut is often interpreted as traumatic injury, gout, reactive or infectious arthritis. The knee, radiocarpal or shoulder joints are most often affected. The lack of typical symmetry forms a false idea of a different nature of the disease. In such cases, synovial fluid analysis, determination of uric acid levels and instrumental methods of examination are important [8].

• **The polymyalgic variant of RA** in older patients may debut with severe pain in the shoulder and pelvic girdle, severe morning stiffness, reminiscent of polymyalgia rheumatica. In such cases, general symptoms dominate: weakness, subfebrile temperature, increased ESR and C-reactive protein. Arthritis of small joints may be absent or occur later. Unlike classical polymyalgia, RA later develops symmetrical arthritis of the hands, erosive changes, and positive anti-CCP [6].

• **Mask of osteoarthritis** in slow-progressing RA with a predominance of degenerative changes of the disease, patients complain of mechanical pain, and laboratory activity of inflammation is minimal. In such cases, only dynamic observation and detection of erosive changes allow to establish the correct diagnosis [11].

• **Fibromyalgia mask.** In some patients, pain syndrome prevails over objective signs of arthritis, which creates a similarity to fibromyalgia. Patients complain of diffuse pain, fatigue, sleep disturbances and depressive symptoms. At the same time, laboratory parameters may remain normal [3].

• **Febrile (septic) mask.** Sometimes RA debuts with prolonged fever, weight loss and a pronounced inflammatory syndrome, which can simulate: sepsis, infective endocarditis, tuberculosis, oncohematological processes. Such patients are often examined for a long time in infectious hospitals. A characteristic feature is the appearance of joint syndrome after several weeks or months [21].

Sometimes extra-articular manifestations of RA precede the development of the typical joint syndrome. Such manifestations include:

- **rheumatoid nodules;**

- **Lung involvement** – the most common pulmonary manifestations are interstitial lung disease, pleurisy, rheumatoid nodules, bronchiectasis. Of particular concern is RA-associated interstitial lung disease (RA-ILD), which may present with cough and shortness of breath in the absence of significant arthritis. Current guidelines emphasize the need for high-resolution computed tomography, pulmonary function tests, and a multidisciplinary evaluation involving a rheumatologist and a pulmonologist [10].

- **Vasculitis**, which manifests as purpura, skin ulcers, polyneuropathy, ischemic lesions, and damage to internal organs. In some cases, vasculitic manifestations are the first clinical sign of a systemic autoimmune process [17].

- **anemia of chronic inflammation;**

- **serositis;**

- **Neuropathies** in RA may include: tunnel neuropathies, cervical myelopathy, polyneuropathy, spinal cord compression in atlantoaxial instability. Sometimes patients are observed for a long time by a neurologist for cervical osteochondrosis, radiculopathy, neuropathic pain [24].

- **Palindromic rheumatism** as a prodrome of RA is characterized by short-term relapses of arthritis with complete inter-attack recovery. In a significant proportion of patients with positive ACCPs, palindromic rheumatism is considered a prodromal stage of RA. The modern concept of "pre-RA" suggests the possibility of early identification of high-risk individuals before the development of persistent synovitis [7].

- **Cardiac mask** in RA can lead to: pericarditis, myocarditis, accelerated atherosclerosis. Sometimes it is the cardiovascular symptoms that dominate the clinical picture [13].

In such situations, patients are observed for a long time by pulmonologists, cardiologists or neurologists without suspicion of rheumatoid arthritis.

The main reasons for late diagnosis are: the absence of typical symmetrical polyarthritis. Seronegativity, the predominance of systemic manifestations, similarity with other diseases [14].

Modern diagnosis of RA is based on the use of the ACR/EULAR 2010 criteria, which take into account: the number of affected joints, serological markers, acute phase indices, and duration of symptoms [20].

Of importance are [1]:

- rheumatoid factor (RF);

- antibodies to cyclic citrullinated peptide (ACCP);

- ESR;

- C-reactive protein.

ACCPs are characterized by high specificity (>95%) for RA and can be determined even before the clinical debut of the disease. However, negative results do not exclude early or seronegative RA [16].

Among instrumental diagnostic methods, radiography in the early stages has limited informative value. More sensitive methods are [23]:

- joint ultrasound;

- magnetic resonance imaging;

- power Doppler.

- CT of the chest for pulmonary manifestations.

These methods allow to detect synovitis, erosions and subclinical inflammation even before the appearance of radiological changes. It is the methods of modern imaging that have become key in the detection of atypical and preclinical forms of RA.

The ACR/EULAR 2010 classification criteria remain the basis for the early diagnosis of RA [8].

The diagnosis of RA is considered probable if the total score is ≥ 6 points according to the criteria: joint involvement, serological markers, acute phase indices, duration of symptoms [18].

Atypical forms of RA should be differentiated from [25]:

- osteoarthritis;

- psoriatic arthritis;

- reactive arthritis;

- gout;

- systemic lupus erythematosus;

- viral arthritis;

- fibromyalgia;

- Lyme arthritis.

Of particular difficulty are overlap syndromes and seronegative variants of the course [3].

Comprehensive analysis of clinical, laboratory and instrumental data allows to avoid diagnostic errors.

Conclusions

Rheumatoid arthritis is a clinically heterogeneous disease with a large number of atypical onsets and "masks". Atypical forms of RA significantly complicate early diagnosis and can lead to erroneous treatment. The greatest difficulties arise with seronegative, febrile, monoarthritic and extraarticular onset of the disease.

Modern approaches to diagnosis are based on a comprehensive analysis of clinical symptoms, serological markers and imaging methods. The concept of "pre-RA" and the implementation of modern EULAR/ACR recommendations open up opportunities for very early detection of the disease and timely appointment of basic therapy. Understanding the clinical "masks" of RA is of important practical importance for doctors of various specialties, since it is early diagnosis that determines the prognosis, quality of life of patients and the risk of disability.

References

1. Aletaha D., Smolen J. S.. Diagnosis and management of rheumatoid arthritis: a review // *JAMA*. 2018. Vol. 320(13). P. 1360–1372.
2. American College of Rheumatology. 2021 American College of Rheumatology Guideline for the Treatment of Rheumatoid Arthritis // *Arthritis Care & Research*. 2021. Vol. 73(7). P. 924–939.

3. Bennett J. L., Isaacs J. D. et al. Rheumatoid sarcomatosis: loss of skeletal muscle strength and mass in rheumatoid arthritis // *Nature Reviews Rheumatology*. 2023. Vol. 19. P. 239–251.
4. Burmester G. R., Pope J. E.. Novel treatment strategies in rheumatoid arthritis // *The Lancet*. 2017. Vol. 389(10086). P. 2338–2348.
5. Conran C., Kolfenbach J., Moreland L. et al. A Review of Difficult-to-Treat Rheumatoid Arthritis: Definition, Clinical Presentation, and Management // *Current Rheumatology Reports*. 2023. Vol. 25(12). P. 285–294.
6. Diaz M. J., Natarelli N., Kaffenberger B. H. et al. Cutaneous Manifestations of Rheumatoid Arthritis: Diagnosis and Treatment // *Journal of Personalized Medicine*. 2023. Vol. 13(10). Article 1479.
7. Ding Q., Hu W., Zhu Y. Z. et al. Signaling pathways in rheumatoid arthritis: implications for targeted therapy // *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*. 2023. Vol. 8. Article 68.
8. European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology. EULAR recommendations for the management of rheumatoid arthritis with synthetic and biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs: 2022 update // *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*. 2023. Vol. 82(1). P. 3–18.
9. Firestein G. S., McInnes I. B.. Immunopathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis // *Immunity*. 2017. Vol. 46(2). P. 183–196.
10. Kelly C. A., Nisar M. et al. Rheumatoid arthritis-related interstitial lung disease: associations, prognostic factors and physiological and radiological characteristics // *Rheumatology*. 2019. Vol. 58(9). P. 1676–1682.
11. Mankia K., Emery P.. Preclinical rheumatoid arthritis: progress toward prevention // *Arthritis & Rheumatology*. 2016. Vol. 68(4). P. 779–788.
12. McInnes I. B., Schett G.. Pathogenetic insights from the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis // *The Lancet*. 2017. Vol. 389(10086). P. 2328–2337.
13. Mitrović J., Hrkač S., Tečar J. et al. Pathogenesis of Extraarticular Manifestations in Rheumatoid Arthritis—A Comprehensive Review // *Biomedicine*. 2023. Vol. 11(5). Article 1262.
14. Ostergaard M., Peterfy C., Conaghan P. et al. MRI and ultrasound in rheumatoid arthritis // *Nature Reviews Rheumatology*. 2020. Vol. 16(1). P. 30–44.
15. Paroli M., Sirinian M. I.. When Autoantibodies Are Missing: The Challenge of Seronegative Rheumatoid Arthritis // *Antibodies*. 2023. Vol. 12(4). Article 69.
16. Rahali F. Z., Tarmidi M., Admou B. et al. Clinical significance of anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide (anti-CCP) antibodies in rheumatoid arthritis: Literature review // *SN Comprehensive Clinical Medicine*. 2023. Vol. 5. Article 272.
17. Small A., Lowe K., Wechalekar M. D.. Immune checkpoints in rheumatoid arthritis: progress and promise // *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2023. Vol. 14. Article 1285554.
18. Smolen J. S., Aletaha D., McInnes I. B.. Rheumatoid arthritis // *The Lancet*. 2016. Vol. 388(10055). P. 2023–2038.
19. Smolen J.S. et al. Global RA treatment recommendations: an update from various international societies. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Rheumatology*. 2024.
20. Smolen J. S., Landewé R. B. M., Aletaha D. et al. EULAR recommendations for the management of rheumatoid arthritis with synthetic and biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs: 2022 update // *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*. 2023. Vol. 82(1). P. 3–18.
21. Turesson C.. Extra-articular rheumatoid arthritis: current concepts // *Current Opinion in Rheumatology*. 2018. Vol. 30(3). P. 300–305.
22. van Steenberghe H. W., Aletaha D., de Wit M. et al. EULAR definition of arthralgia suspicious for progression to rheumatoid arthritis // *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*. 2017. Vol. 76(3). P. 491–496.
23. World Health Organization. Chronic rheumatic conditions: rheumatoid arthritis update. Geneva: WHO, 2023.
24. Yehudina Y.D., Trypilka S. Elderly-onset rheumatoid arthritis — clinical findings and treatment features. *Pain Joints Spine*. 2024.
25. 2024 update of the recommendations of the French Society of Rheumatology for the diagnosis and management of patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Joint Bone Spine*. 2024.